

Chemical Examination of some Wild Leguminous Seeds

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The chemical composition and the water soluble carbohydrates and total soluble reducing substances at room temperature as well as at 100° from five non-edible wild Indian leguminous seeds have been quantitatively and qualitatively studied and compared.

LITERATURE survey¹ of wild leguminous seeds reveals that they are the chief source of proteins and carbohydrates in Indian diet. The present communication reports a comparative chemical analysis of five non-cultivated leguminous seeds, *Psoralia corylifolia*, *Butea monosperma*, *Bauhinia variegata*, *Abrus precatorious*, and *Lathyrus sativus* of Bundelkhand region of Central India.

Experimental

The experimental legumes were collected locally and from the different parts of Bundelkhand region in Central India and botanically identified. The seeds were cleaned and powdered to 100 mesh and defatted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°). Moisture, ash, water soluble ash, acid soluble ash, crude fibre and fat contents were determined by standard methods². Nitrogen was determined by micro-Kjeldahl's method and from the result, percentage of crude protein was calculated. Ether extractives were determined by usual methods (Table 1). Extraction of defatted seed meals for the determination of total water soluble carbohydrates and total

soluble reducing substances were estimated by the method of Hagedorn and Jenson as described by Hawk *et al.*⁴ and modified by Howden and Kilby⁵ (Table 2).

TABLE 2—TOTAL SOLUBLE CARBOHYDRATE AND TOTAL SOLUBLE REDUCING SUBSTANCES OF THE SEEDS

Sl. no.	Seeds*	(g glucose/100 g seed)			
		Total carbohydrates		Total reducing substances	
		27 ± 3°	100°	27 ± 3°	100°
1.	<i>P.c</i>	11.96	20.20	3.14	3.72
2.	<i>B.m</i>	13.98	24.52	1.86	2.04
3.	<i>B.v</i>	19.92	29.12	3.06	3.01
4.	<i>A.p</i>	9.91	18.72	2.18	2.43
5.	<i>L.s</i>	18.20	20.16	4.09	4.15

* Explanation as in Table 1.

Qualitative analysis of soluble sugars was performed by employing paper partition chromatography technique of Consden *et al.*⁶ as described by Partridge⁷. A large number of different solvent systems^{8,9} have been used for the separation of carbohydrates and in the present investigation the following solvent systems were employed: phenol (98% w/v)-ammonia saturated, propan-1-ol-ethyl acetate-water (7:1:2)¹⁰, butan-1-ol-acetic acid-water (4:1:5)¹¹, ethyl acetate-pyridine-water (2:1:2)¹² and ethyl acetate-pyridine-water (12:5:4)¹³. When the solvent mixture formed layers, the upper layer was employed for the development of the chromatogram and the lower layer for saturation of the interior of the chromatographic tank.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows, the wild non-edible leguminous seeds contain 24.5-41.65% crude protein which indicates their possible inclusion in animal nutrition.

Table 2 shows, non-edible leguminous seeds contain 9.91-19.92% water soluble carbohydrate extracted at room temperature and 1.86-4.09% total reducing substances. The slight increase of reducing substances at 100° could be due to the release of reducing sugars by hydrolysis of polysaccharides in presence of mineral salts of seed origin.

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE SEEDS*
(Percentage dry weight basis)

Sl. no.	Constituents	<i>P.c</i>	<i>B.m</i>	<i>B.v</i>	<i>A.p</i>	<i>L.s</i>
1.	Moisture	4.08	6.86	3.90	5.06	9.10
2.	Ash	5.14	6.84	4.48	5.98	7.96
	Water soluble	13.20	15.10	7.80	10.42	11.25
	Acid soluble	33.40	29.40	31.90	18.32	17.98
3.	Fat	8.52	11.04	11.40	3.92	7.84
4.	Nitrogen	5.88	3.92	4.312	6.272	6.664
5.	Crude protein	36.75	24.50	26.95	39.20	41.65
6.	Crude fibre	12.06	3.20	11.82	9.08	2.70
7.	Carbohydrates	37.54	54.46	44.95	42.42	40.45

* *P.c*=*Psoralia corylifolia*, *B.m*=*Butea monosperma*, *B.v*=*Bauhinia variegata*, *A.p*=*Abrus precatorious*, *L.s*=*Lathyrus sativus*.

soluble reducing substances was made by the usual method at room temperature (27 ± 3°) as well as at 100°. Total soluble carbohydrate was estimated by the method of Trevelyn and Harrison³. Total

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Although the nature of the residual reducing substances is not very clear, the free amino acids, ascorbic acids and carbohydrates and also keto groups appear to be the main reducing substances present in seeds. In addition, flavonoids, alkaloids, leucoanthocyanines and other seed pigments possessing phenolic properties as referred^{14,15} could be the other contributing factor.

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